

Viscosity of Some Mono Monovalent Salts in Dioxane Water Mixtures at 35°

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The viscosity of solutions of potassium nitrate, sodium nitrate, sodium bromate and potassium iodate in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane water mixtures have been reported. The 'B' coefficient for different solutions have been recorded and the influence of the anions in such solutions are discussed.

The viscosity of some mono-monovalent electrolytes in dioxane water mixtures have been reported earlier^{1,3,4}. The present work was undertaken with a view to study the influence of ions specially anions on the solvents. The salts chosen are potassium nitrate, sodium nitrate, sodium bromate and potassium iodate and the solvents are dioxan-water mixtures containing 10, 20 and 30% dioxane by weight.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were E. Merck 'extrapure' quality. The salts were recrystallised, dried and kept in vacuum. Purification of dioxan, preparation of solution and other experimental details were as reported previously¹.

TABLE I

Comparison of observed and calculated values of η/η_0 at two concentrations

Solvent composition % of dioxane	10			20			30		
	Conc. moles/litre	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calc.	Conc. moles/litre	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calc.	Conc. moles/litre	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calc.
KNO ₃	0.0713	1.0027	1.0026	0.0752	1.0047	1.0044	0.0512	1.0023	1.0024
	0.0642	1.0016	1.0014	0.0642	1.0042	1.0043	0.0455	1.0014	1.0011
NaNO ₃	0.0774	1.0084	1.0084	0.0641	1.0088	1.0087	0.0811	1.0150	1.0152
	0.0521	1.0069	1.0068	0.0421	1.0060	1.0062	0.0612	1.0115	1.0114
NaBrO ₃	0.0521	1.0060	1.0061	0.0556	1.0073	1.0075	0.0612	1.0085	1.0084
	0.0384	1.0047	1.0045	0.0284	1.0042	1.0041	0.0413	1.0059	1.0058
KIO ₃	0.0756	1.0133	1.0135	0.0873	1.0162	1.0166	0.0625	1.0130	1.0134
	0.0541	1.0107	1.0109	0.0534	1.0108	1.0106	0.0400	1.0092	1.0089

1. R. C. Acharya, P. K. Das and D. Patnaik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 56.
2. H. Falkenhagen and E. L. Vernon, *Phil. Mag.*, 1932, **14**(7), 537.
3. P. K. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 613.
4. P. K. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 341.

DISCUSSION

The experimental data of η/η_0 at two concentrations for each of the electrolyte studied as well as the calculated values with the help of the Jones-Dole equation in ten and twenty percent of the solvents and the modified Jones-Dole equation¹ for thirty percent of the solvent are given in Table I. The values of 'A', 'B' and 'X' have been determined in the usual manner¹ and are presented in Table II together with the theoretical value of 'A' calculated using the Falkenhagen Vernon's equation².

TABLE II
Values of A, B and X

% of dioxan in solvent	10			20			30		
	'A' Cal.	'A'Obs.	'B'	'A' Cal.	'A'Obs.	'B'	'A'Cal.	'B'	X
KNO ₃	0.0059	0.0060	0.015	0.0062	0.0067	0.0385	0.0050	0.050	1.02
NaNO ₃	0.0063	0.0064	0.085	0.0066	0.0068	0.1085	0.0080	0.163	1.01
NaBrO ₃	0.0066	0.0065	0.089	0.0062	0.0063	0.1090	0.0081	0.119	1.025
KIO ₃	0.0067	0.0072	0.152	0.0072	0.0078	0.1640	0.0088	0.165	1.04

The Jones-Dole equation is found to be obeyed for all the salts in ten and twenty percent dioxane solutions and the value of 'A' found from experimental data agrees well with the value calculated theoretically. In thirty percent dioxane solutions the modified Jones-Dole equation holds good, the value of 'X' being slightly greater than unity. It is seen from Table II that the value of 'B' is positive for all the electrolytes examined.

Cox and Wolfender⁵, Kaminsky⁶ and Gurney⁷ have partitioned the value of 'B' amongst ions. The ionic 'B' values have been calculated by the author on the lines of Kaminsky and are given in Table III. Any ion which by suitable orientation increases the order of water molecules in the diffused layer of the cosphere of the ion has a positive value of 'B'.

TABLE III

% of dioxan in solvent	<i>Individual ionic values of the B coefficient</i>						
	K ⁺	Na ⁺	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	BrO ₃ ⁻	IO ₃ ⁻
10	0.0100	0.0810	0.0100	0.0240	0.005	0.008	0.142
20	0.0199	0.0921	0.0199	0.0311	0.0186	0.0169	0.144
30	0.0263	0.1397	0.0263	0.0351	0.0237	0.036	0.1487

5. W. M. Cox and J. H. Wolfenden, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1934, **A145**, 475.

6. M. Kaminsky, *Disc. Faraday. Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 171.

7. R. W. Gurney, *Ionic Process in solution*, McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., 1953, 160.

Any component of a solvent which increases order has the same effect but the matter is not so simple. Dioxane increases the value of 'B' as may be seen from Table III, but there is slight decrease in the value of 'B' for Na^+ , when we pass from pure water to dioxane. It may be noted that the value of 'B' for negative ions given in Table III are in the order $\text{IO}_3^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{BrO}_3^- > \text{NO}_3^-$ in ten percent dioxane. The high value of 'B' for IO_3^- may be due to large ionic volume of IO_3^- .

The order given above could not have been predicted on the basis of an existing knowledge. This order is not maintained when the % of dioxane increases. In 20% dioxane $\text{NO}_3^- > \text{BrO}_3^-$ and in 30% dioxane $\text{BrO}_3^- > \text{Br}^-$ and $\text{BrO}_3^- > \text{NO}_3^-$.

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